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The Role of Artillery Reconnaissance in Conduct of Counterbattery Combat

Maksudov Odiljon Arifjanovich

Academy of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan senior teacher of the department,
associate professor

Abstract: *In given article are opened a role of artillery intelligence at conducting counterbattery struggle. Are analysed strong and weaknesses of each kind of artillery intelligence at conducting counterbattery struggle.*

Keywords: *artillery intelligence, forces and means of artillery intelligence, an intelligence field, intelligence system, an intelligence strip, optical intelligence, radar intelligence, air intelligence.*

It is difficult to imagine armed conflicts on Earth without artillery, which is considered the main, and in some cases, the only means of causing damage from a distance.

Artillery damage to the enemy in battle is carried out in order to reduce its combat potential and gain the advantage of opening fire.

The question arises, what does it mean to reduce combat capability and gain fire superiority?

Decreasing the combat potential of the enemy means that he:

it is achieved by limiting their ability for a certain period of time or completely by causing damage to the means of opening fire during the execution of the maneuver.

Gaining the advantage of firing is achieved by inflicting effective losses on the enemy artillery before or after it begins firing.

Dear participants of the conference, as a result of the first attempt to destroy the enemy's artillery in battle, a counter-battery fight occurs.

Counter-battery is the process from the moment enemy artillery is detected to the execution of fire to destroy it.

Modern versions of battery fighting:

modern artillery reconnaissance means;
automated fire control system;
modern means of damage and high precision
refers to ammunition.

Dear conference participants!!!

All of the above-mentioned elements are directly related to each other, and they ensure the increase in the survivability and effective use of artillery.

However, if the reconnaissance, which is the eye of the artillery in the battle, is not properly organized or not carried out effectively, then it is inevitable that this artillery unit will be destroyed as the first target of the enemy's artillery.

The Russia-Ukraine armed conflict, which has been ongoing since February 2022, shows that counter-battery will play an important role in the battle. There are optical, air, radar and sound reconnaissance types of artillery reconnaissance, and almost all types are used in counter-battery combat.

Today, the head of state and the leadership of the Ministry of Defense pay special attention to increasing the combat potential of artillery, taking into account the military-political situation and existing threats, in particular, the "Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on "Strengthening the security and defense potential of our country, conducting an open, pragmatic and active foreign policy." as the 90th goal of the seventh priority direction called "To further strengthen the state's defense capabilities, to strengthen the combat readiness of the Armed Forces, its capabilities and capabilities." marked.

The above shows the relevance of the topic "The role of artillery reconnaissance in counter-battery warfare".

Artillery reconnaissance in counter-battery combat:

finding (determining) the location of enemy artillery;
determining its character and coordinates, preparing necessary information for artillery fire;
transmission of information to the firing position;
monitor the results of the damage;
performs the most basic tasks, such as correction of artillery fire.

An analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of each type of artillery reconnaissance in performing the above tasks shows the following, in particular:

Optical Reconnaissance in Battery Combat:

Taking into account that the artillery of the battalion, brigade and higher ranks of the enemy usually occupy the area of the firing position at a depth of 500 m to 7-8 km, optical reconnaissance in favorable weather conditions is also an effective reconnaissance tool in counter-battery combat.

Currently, private companies that manufacture weapons and military equipment for the military needs of armies have produced various modern optical reconnaissance tools designed to conduct artillery reconnaissance, information about some of them is given in the slide. .

There is also a laser rangefinder type of optical reconnaissance, which is used in the use of high-precision ammunition.

Advantages of optical reconnaissance:

1. When determining the location of enemy artillery, all information is determined digitally based on real observation.
2. Protected from enemy intelligence
3. It is possible to conduct reconnaissance at night (if night vision devices are available).
4. It does not take a lot of time to put reconnaissance vehicles into combat and walking condition and to prepare them for work.
5. Modern optical reconnaissance tools indicate the target by laser light for high-precision ammunition.

Disadvantages:

1. The possibility of use in adverse weather conditions (fog, snow, rain, storm, etc.) is limited.
2. There is no possibility of full monitoring of the results of damage (relative to drones).
3. It is not possible to detect the enemy's artillery's hidden maneuver (at night, due to the natural elevations of the place).
4. Optical reconnaissance cannot detect batteries in firing positions located at a depth.

Radar reconnaissance in counter-battery:

Radar reconnaissance is the most effective tool in counter-battery warfare.

Currently, the parties to the armed conflict in Ukraine are effectively using radar intelligence in counter-battery. This shows that conducting reconnaissance with this type of artillery reconnaissance is one of the promising directions.

The projectile determines the position of firing at the enemy battery and the coordinates of the drop point of the projectile (mine) by advancing the trajectory of the mine 3-4 times, and the artillery fire is corrected.

Advantages:

detects and tracks flying artillery shells, mines, rocket-propelled grenades and tactical missiles;
finds the coordinates of the take-off and landing points of the projectiles with high accuracy;
determines the class and caliber of weapons in the firing positions that are firing;
determines the firing position of several artillery batteries performing the firing task at the same time;
effectively locates enemy artillery batteries even in adverse weather conditions;
along with identifying the enemy's batteries in the firing position, he corrects the artillery fire.
simultaneously works in reconnaissance and control mode.

Disadvantages:

effective against the enemy's radio-electronic intelligence;

due to the size and weight of some radar reconnaissance vehicles, it takes a lot of time to put them into a combat (walking) position, to maneuver and to eliminate minor malfunctions that occur during use.

Air reconnaissance in counter-battery:

The history of the first use of aerial reconnaissance in counter-battery warfare dates back to the American Civil War in 1861-65. for the first time in military history, Teddeus Lau raised an aerostat to a height of 91 m and tied it to a tree with a rope in order to monitor the movements of enemy troops and their positions on the battlefield. During the First and Second World Wars and other armed conflicts, aerostats, airplanes, and helicopters were widely used to determine the firing position of enemy artillery and correct firing. It is no exaggeration to say that in today's modern armed conflicts, drones are fully responsible for this task.

Advantages:

constant combat readiness and mobility;

presents the location of the firing position of the enemy artillery battery in the form of video (photo) information in real time;

quickly determines the character of the target, its coordinates and shooting settings (mostly);

directs high-precision ammunition to the target using a laser beam (some);

allows you to monitor the claim process in real time;

the small size of drones and the ability to stay in a suspended position for a certain time (copters) cause difficulties in their detection and observation by enemy air defense means.

cheap compared to other reconnaissance (radiolocation reconnaissance, sound reconnaissance) and enemy artillery battery weapons.

Disadvantages:

the possibility of use in adverse weather conditions is limited;

limited time for conducting air reconnaissance;

the enemy's susceptibility to radio-electronic warfare;

Sound intelligence in battery combat:

The history of the first use of sound reconnaissance in anti-battery warfare dates back to the years after the Russo-Japanese war. It was invented in 1909 by Nikolai Benau, a soldier of the Russian army. In the armies of other countries, sound reconnaissance appeared a few years later. For example, it was created in the German and French armies in 1915, in the British army in 1916, and in the American army in 1917.

One of the most important data is that 70% of enemy artillery batteries identified during World War II were accounted for by sound reconnaissance.

In the years after the war, special attention was paid to the development of sound intelligence and it was improved.

Voice reconnaissance mainly performed two tasks:

1. Reconnaissance of unobserved firing positions regardless of the type of projectile (mine) used by artillery and mortars, as well as its position through the sound wave generated when the rocket artillery projectile flies out of the guidance package.
2. Correction of artillery firing by following the sound of explosions at the point of impact of shells (mines).

Advantages:

high maneuverability, mobility of the sound reconnaissance complex and availability of tracking equipment;

implementation of the "reconnaissance-reconnaissance" cycle of the automated sound intelligence complex in a short time.

Disadvantages:

the weakness of sound intelligence to detect artificial sounds created by the enemy on the battlefield;

sensitivity of intelligence tools to the sounds generated by the use of active-reactive, cluster, smoke-inducing, propaganda shells by enemy artillery units;

low accuracy of finding the firing position of enemy artillery units.

Based on the study and analysis of the role, advantages and disadvantages of artillery reconnaissance in counter-battery combat, the following can be **concluded**:

1. When artillery units perform firing duties from a closed firing position during combat operations, counter-battery combat is unthinkable without artillery reconnaissance forces and means.
2. An analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of artillery reconnaissance types requires the formation of a unit that includes all its types in order for artillery reconnaissance units to perform their tasks effectively.
3. Short-term damage to an enemy artillery battery requires research on the issues of increasing its survivability.

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